

GENERALIZATIONS OF YOUNG-TYPE INEQUALITIES VIA QUADRATIC INTERPOLATION

Phan Thi Minh¹, Tran Quynh Mai², Duong Quoc Huy³

Received Date: 15/5/2022; Revised Date: 10/10/2022; Accepted for Publication: 11/10/2022

SUMMARY

In this paper, we give some new improvements of the famous works of F. Kittaneh, Y. Manasrah about Young's inequalities published on the J. Math. Anal. Appl. (2010) and Linear Multilinear Algebra (2011) via the theory of quadratic interpolations. As applications, we also establish corresponding inequalities for matrix and operator versions.

Keywords: *Young inequality, Convexity, Positive operator, Positive definite Matrix.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The classical Young inequality for scalars states that for all $a, b > 0$ and $\nu \in [0, 1]$, we have

$$(1 - \nu)a + \nu b \geq a^{1-\nu}b^\nu, \quad (1)$$

with equality if and only if $a = b$. The inequality (1) is also known in the literature as the weighted arithmetic-geometric mean inequality.

One of the most striking refinements and reverses of (1) was established by Kittaneh and Manasrahin (Kittaneh & Manasrah, 2010, 2011) as

$$\begin{aligned} r_0(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 + a^{1-\nu}b^\nu \\ \leq (1 - \nu)a + \nu b \\ \leq a^{1-\nu}b^\nu + R_0(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

here and hereafter $r_0 = \min\{\nu, 1 - \nu\}$ and $R_0 = \max\{\nu, 1 - \nu\}$. The equality sign in (2) also happen when $a = b$.

Relying on the proof of these inequalities, we can not see fully the source of non-negative quantities $r_0(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2$ and $R_0(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2$ in (2). However, this will be explained more clearly when applying the well-known Jensen-type inequalities:

$$\begin{aligned} r_0 \left(\frac{\varphi(0) + \varphi(1)}{2} - \varphi\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \right) \\ \leq (1 - \nu)\varphi(0) + \nu\varphi(1) - \varphi(\nu) \\ \leq R_0 \left(\frac{\varphi(0) + \varphi(1)}{2} - \varphi\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

for the convex function $\varphi(\nu) = a^{1-\nu}b^\nu$ with $a, b > 0$ and $\nu \in [0, 1]$. The inequalities in (3) were proposed by Dragomir (Dragomir, 2006). The approach via the convexity of functions not only explain the source of (2), but also provide a unified method for many recent results related to Young's inequality, its refinements and reverses,

see (ChoiKrnicić, & Pecarić, 2017) and references therein.

In this article, we proceed to use the convexity of functions to give a more further refinements of (2). To see this idea clearly, we focus primarily on the case $a \neq b$. The left-hand inequality in (2) is then equivalent to

$$f(\nu) := \frac{(1 - \nu)a + \nu b - a^{1-\nu}b^\nu}{(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2} \geq r_0 \text{ for all } \nu \in [0, 1]$$

Evidently, f is a concave function on $[0, 1]$ because, for all $\nu \in [0, 1]$,

$$f''(\nu) = -a^{1-\nu}b^\nu \left(\frac{\ln a - \ln b}{\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b}} \right)^2 \leq 0.$$

It is easy to see that $r_0 = \min\{\nu, 1 - \nu\}$ is a concave function on $[0, 1]$; moreover, it is a concave interpolation of f on $[0, 1]$ with nodes $0, \frac{1}{2}, 1$. However, if we only consider the interval $[0, \frac{1}{2}]$, the function $r_0 = \nu$ is only a linear interpolation of the function f . This shows that the function given by

$$g(\nu) := \frac{(1 - \nu)a + \nu b - a^{1-\nu}b^\nu}{(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2} - \nu$$

is still concave on $[0, \frac{1}{2}]$. This, together with the

above mentioned idea, motivates us to find a concave interpolation h of the function g on the interval $[0, \frac{1}{2}]$ such that, for all $\nu \in [0, \frac{1}{2}]$,

$$h(\nu) \geq 0 \text{ and } g(\nu) \geq h(\nu).$$

In the present paper, we give a concave interpolation of the quadratic form

¹Phan Chu Trinh High School, Cu Jut, Dak Nong;

²Office of Academic Affairs, Tay Nguyen University, Dak Lak;

³Faculty of Natural Science and Technology, Tay Nguyen University, Dak Lak.

Corresponding author: Duong Quoc Huy; Tel: 0905616183; Email: duongquochuy@ttn.edu.vn

$$h(v) = \alpha v \left(\frac{1}{2} - v\right), \quad \forall v \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right],$$

for some $\alpha > 0$. The similar situation is also considered for the interval $\left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$. Here is also the main goal of the paper which allow us to construct the better refinements of (2).

2. RESEARCH CONTENTS & METHODS

2.1. Research contents

The contents of the article focus on improving scalar versions of Young-type inequalities and apply these inequalities to the theory of matrices and operators. These results give refinements and reverses of some of the recent inequalities established by many mathematicians.

2.2. Research methods

In this article, we use the following methods:

- The theory of convex functions and derivative tools of one variable functions for comparing different functions;
- The quadratic interpolation theory for supplying some new refinements and reverses of Young-type inequalities.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Some new scalar refinements and reverses of Young-type inequalities

The following theorem gives us a refinement of the inequalities in (2).

Theorem 3.1. *If $0 < m \leq a, b \leq M < \infty$ and $0 \leq v \leq 1$, we then have*

$$\begin{aligned} a^{1-v}b^v + r(v)(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 \\ \leq (1-v)a + vb \\ \leq a^{1-v}b^v + R(v)(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where

$$r(v) = r_0 + 2\frac{m}{M}r_0(1/2 - r_0)$$

and

$$R(v) = R_0 - 2\frac{m}{M}r_0(1/2 - r_0).$$

Proof. The inequalities in (4) are obvious when $a = b$. It suffices to consider the case $a \neq b$. In this case, the first inequality in (4) is equivalent

$$\text{to } g(v) := \frac{(1-v)a + vb - a^{1-v}b^v}{(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2} - r(v) \geq 0$$

for all $v \in [0, 1]$. Clearly, if $v \in \left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right]$, then

$$\begin{aligned} g(v) &= \frac{(1-v)a + vb - a^{1-v}b^v}{(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2} \\ &\quad - v - 2\frac{m}{M}v(1/2 - v), \end{aligned}$$

and if $v \in \left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$, then

$$\begin{aligned} g(v) &= \frac{(1-v)a + vb - a^{1-v}b^v}{(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2} \\ &\quad - (1-v) - 2\frac{m}{M}(1-v)(v - 1/2). \end{aligned}$$

By computing directly, we get the second order derivative of g as

$$g''(v) = -a^{1-v}b^v \left(\frac{\ln a - \ln b}{\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b}}\right)^2 + 4\frac{m}{M}.$$

On the other hand, by applying the classical Cauchy mean value theorem, it is easy to see that there exists a constant c being between a and b such that

$$\frac{\ln a - \ln b}{\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{c}} \geq \frac{2}{\sqrt{M}},$$

which implies

$$\left(\frac{\ln a - \ln b}{\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b}}\right)^2 \geq \frac{4}{M}.$$

This leads to that, for all $v \in [0, 1]$,

$$g''(v) \leq -4\frac{a^{1-v}b^v}{M} + 4\frac{m}{M} \leq 0.$$

Therefore, the function g is concave on each interval $\left[0, \frac{1}{2}\right]$ and $\left[\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$ with the property

$g(0) = g\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = g(1) = 0$. This implies $g(v) \geq 0$ fall all $v \in [0, 1]$, which finishes the proof of the first inequality.

From the first inequality in (4), we have, for all $v \in [0, 1]$

$$va + (1-v)b \geq a^vb^{1-v} + r(v)(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2.$$

Using this inequality and the first inequality in (4), we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} (1-v)a + vb &= a + b - [va + (1-v)b] \\ &\leq a + b - a^vb^{1-v} - r(v)(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 n \\ &= [1 - r(v)](\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 + 2\sqrt{ab} - a^vb^{1-v} n \\ &\leq R(v)(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 + a^{1-v}b^v, \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof.

Remark 3.2. After improving (1) to the first

inequality in (2), Kittaneh and Manasrah got the following refinement

$$\begin{aligned} &R_0(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 + H_\nu(a, b) \\ &\geq \frac{a+b}{2} \\ &\geq H_\nu(a, b) + r_0(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 \\ &\geq H_\nu(a, b) \geq \sqrt{ab}, \end{aligned}$$

where $H_\nu(a, b)$ is the Heinz mean in parameter ν of two non-negative real numbers a and b given by

$$H_\nu(a, b) = \frac{a^{1-\nu}b^\nu + a^\nu b^{1-\nu}}{2}.$$

Since the inequalities in (4) are better than (2), we obtain the following better refinements and reverses

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{a+b}{2} &\geq H_\nu(a, b) + r(\nu)(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 \\ &\geq H_\nu(a, b) + r_0(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 \quad (5) \\ &\geq H_\nu(a, b) \\ &\geq \sqrt{ab}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} &R_0(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 + H_\nu(a, b) \\ &\geq R(\nu)(\sqrt{a} - \sqrt{b})^2 + H_\nu(a, b) \quad (6) \\ &\geq \frac{a+b}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Here, the quadratic functions $r(\nu)$ and $R(\nu)$ are as in Theorem 3.1.

Kittaneh and Manasrah established in (Kittaneh & Manasrah, 2010, 2011) the refinement and reverse as follows

$$4H_\nu(a, b)^2 + 2r_0(a - b)^2 \leq (a + b)^2$$

and

$$4H_\nu(a, b)^2 + 2R_0(a - b)^2 \geq (a + b)^2.$$

The following corollary give us two refinements of these inequalities.

Corollary 3.3. *If $0 < m \leq a, b \leq M < \infty$ and $\nu \in [0, 1]$, we then have*

$$4H_\nu(a, b)^2 + 2r(\nu)(a - b)^2 \leq (a + b)^2, \quad (7)$$

and

$$4H_\nu(a, b)^2 + 2R(\nu)(a - b)^2 \geq (a + b)^2, \quad (8)$$

where $r(\nu)$ and $R(\nu)$ are as in Theorem 3.1.

Proof. We first give a proof of (7). Indeed, by Theorem 3.1, we can rewrite (7) and obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &(a + b)^2 - (a^{1-\nu}b^\nu + a^\nu b^{1-\nu})^2 \\ &= a^2 + b^2 - a^{2(1-\nu)}b^{2\nu} - a^{2\nu}b^{2(1-\nu)} \\ &= (1-\nu)a^2 + \nu b^2 - a^{2(1-\nu)}b^{2\nu} \\ &\quad + \nu a^2 + (1-\nu)b^2 - a^{2\nu}b^{2(1-\nu)} \\ &\geq r(\nu)(a - b)^2 + r(\nu)(a - b)^2 \\ &= 2r(\nu)(a - b)^2. \end{aligned}$$

The proof of (8) is similar to that of (7), so we omit the details here.

We finish this subsection by a different approach basing on the Jensen-Dragomir inequality (Dragomir, 2006) as follows.

Remark 3.4. Let us consider the function $g(\nu) = \frac{M}{2}\nu^2 - f(\nu)$ defined on $[0, 1]$, where $M = \max\{a, b\}(\ln \frac{b}{a})^2$ and $f(\nu) = a^{1-\nu}b^\nu$. It is easy to see that

$$g''(\nu) = M - a^{1-\nu}b^\nu \left(\ln \frac{b}{a}\right)^2 \geq 0,$$

which shows that g is convex on $[0, 1]$. Then, by Jensen-Dragomir's inequality, we get, for all $x, y \in [0, 1]$,

$$\begin{aligned} &(1-\nu)f(x) + \nu f(y) - f((1-\nu)x + \nu y) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2}M\nu(1-\nu)(x - y)^2. \end{aligned}$$

Applying this inequality, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned} f\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) &\geq \frac{f(\nu) + f(1-\nu)}{2} - \frac{M}{8}(1-2\nu)^2 \\ &\geq \frac{f(0) + f(1)}{2} - \frac{M}{8} \\ &\geq \frac{f(\nu) + f(1-\nu)}{2} - \frac{M}{8}. \end{aligned}$$

That is,

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{ab} &\geq H_\nu(a, b) - \frac{M}{8}(1-2\nu)^2 \\ &\geq \frac{a+b}{2} - \frac{M}{8} \\ &\geq H_\nu(a, b) - \frac{M}{8} \\ &\geq \sqrt{ab} - \frac{M}{8}. \end{aligned}$$

3.2. Some new operator refinements and reverses of Young-type inequalities

The main goal of this subsection is to establish operator versions of inequalities in Theorem 3.1. We first recall some necessary concepts and notations. We will use the uppercase letters for

operators on a complex Hilbert space H . In particular, I stands for the identity operator on H . We also utilize the following notations:

(i) $A \geq 0$ ($A > 0$) is a positive (invertible positive) operator;

(ii) $A \geq B$ ($A > B$) if $A - B$ is a positive (invertible positive) operator.

For $\nu \in [0,1]$, the ν -weighted arithmetic and geometric means of an invertible positive operator A and a positive operator B are defined respectively as

$$A\nabla_{\nu}B = (1-\nu)A + \nu B,$$

$$A\sharp_{\nu}B = A^{1/2}(A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2})^{\nu}A^{1/2}.$$

We write $A\nabla B$ and $A\sharp B$ for $A\nabla_{1/2}B$ and $A\sharp_{1/2}B$, respectively.

For matrix versions of concepts and definitions, the reader can find in (Choi et al., 2017; Kittaneh & Manasrah, 2010, 2011).

Matrix version of (1) says that

$$A\sharp_{\nu}B \leq A\nabla_{\nu}B,$$

where $\nu \in [0,1]$ and A, B are positive definite.

After improving (1) to the refinement and reverse (2), Kittaneh and Manasrah (Kittaneh & Manasrah, 2010, 2011) established the matrix versions of the form

$$2r_0(A\nabla B - A\sharp B) + A\sharp_{\nu}B \leq A\nabla_{\nu}B$$

$$\leq 2R_0(A\nabla B - A\sharp B) + A\sharp_{\nu}B, \quad (9)$$

with $A, B > 0$ and $\nu \in [0,1]$.

Based on the improvements in Theorem 3.1, we can state the main results in this subsection which are refinements of (9) as follows.

Theorem 3.5. *Let A and B be invertible positive operators with their spectra in the interval $[m, M]$ with $0 < m \leq M < \infty$. For $\nu \in [0,1]$, we have*

$$2r(\nu)(A\nabla B - A\sharp B) + A\sharp_{\nu}B \leq A\nabla_{\nu}B$$

$$\leq 2R(\nu)(A\nabla B - A\sharp B) + A\sharp_{\nu}B, \quad (10)$$

where $r(\nu)$ and $R(\nu)$ are as in Theorem 3.1.

To prove the theorem, we need the following.

Lemma 3.6. (Zhao & Wu, 2015) *Let X be an arbitrary self-adjoint operator. If f and g are continuous real-valued functions on the spectrum $\text{Sp}(X)$ satisfying that $f(t) \geq g(t)$ for all $t \in \text{Sp}(X)$, then have an operator inequality $f(X) \geq g(X)$.*

Proof of Theorem 3.5. In view of (4), we have, for all $x \in [\frac{m}{M}, \frac{M}{m}]$,

$$x^{\nu} + r(\nu)(1+x-2\sqrt{x})$$

$$\leq (1-\nu) + \nu x$$

$$\leq x^{\nu} + R(\nu)(1+x-2\sqrt{x}).$$

This, together with Lemma 3.6, leads that, for every invertible positive operator X with its spectrum $\text{Sp}(X)$ of X in $[\frac{m}{M}, \frac{M}{m}]$, the following inequalities hold

$$X^{\nu} + r(\nu)(I + X - 2X^{1/2})$$

$$\leq (1-\nu)I + \nu X \quad (11)$$

$$\leq X^{\nu} + R(\nu)(I + X - 2X^{1/2}).$$

Since the spectra of A, B are in the interval $[m, M]$, the spectrum of $A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2}$ is in $[\frac{m}{M}, \frac{M}{m}]$. Therefore, replacing X in (11) with $A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2}$, we get

$$(A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2})^{\nu} + r(\nu)(I + A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2}$$

$$- 2(A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2})^{1/2})$$

$$\leq (1-\nu)I + \nu(A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2}) \quad (12)$$

$$\leq (A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2})^{\nu} + R(\nu)(I + (A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2})$$

$$- 2(A^{-1/2}BA^{-1/2})^{1/2}),$$

Multiplying the inequalities in (12) by $A^{1/2}$ both-sidely, we obtain the desired inequalities in (10)

3.3. Some new matrix refinements of Youngtype inequalities

In this subsection, we use $M_n(\mathbb{C})$ to denote the space $n \times n$ complex matrices. Recall that for $A \in M_n(\mathbb{C})$ the singular values

$$s_1(A) \geq s_2(A) \geq \dots \geq s_n(A)$$

of A are the eigenvalues of positive semidefinite matrix $|A| := (A^*A)^{1/2}$, where A^* is the adjoint matrix of A . the trace of a matrix $A = (a_{ij}) \in M_n(\mathbb{C})$ is defined by

$$\text{tr } A = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{ii}.$$

However, following (Kittaneh & Manasrah, 2010), it can also be computed via Schatten 1-norm by

$$\text{tr } A = \| |A| \|_1 = \sum_{j=1}^n s_j(A).$$

The following lemma gives us an inequality on the trace of matrices.

Lemma 3.7. (Manasrah & Kittaneh, 2015) *Let $A, B \in M_n(\mathbb{C})$ be positive semidefinite. If $\nu \in [0,1]$, then*

$$\operatorname{tr} | A^{1-\nu} B^\nu | \leq (\operatorname{tr} A)^{1-\nu} (\operatorname{tr} B)^\nu.$$

The following two theorems provide refinements of Young-type inequalities for traces and determinants of matrices.

Theorem 3.8. *Let $0 < m < M < \infty$ and $A, B \in M_n(\mathbb{C})$ be positive definite with their spectra in the interval $[m, M]$. If $\nu \in [0, 1]$, we then have*

$$\operatorname{tr} | A^{1-\nu} B^\nu | + r(\nu)(\sqrt{\operatorname{tr} A} - \sqrt{\operatorname{tr} B})^2 \leq \operatorname{tr}((1-\nu)A + \nu B), \quad (13)$$

Where $r(\nu)$ is as Theorem 3.1.

Proof. The proof of (13) directly follows from the first inequality in Theorem 3.1 and Lemma 3.7 by taking $a = \operatorname{tr} A$ and $b = \operatorname{tr} B$, so we omit to present the details here.

Theorem 3.9. *Let $0 < m < M < \infty$ and $A, B \in M_n(\mathbb{C})$ be positive definite with their spectra in the interval $[m, M]$. If $\nu \in [0, 1]$, we then have*

$$\det(A^{1-\nu} B^\nu) + [2\tau(\nu)]^n \det(A\nabla B - A\sharp B) \leq \det((1-\nu)A + \nu B), \quad (14)$$

where

$$\tau(\nu) = r_0 + 2 \frac{m^2}{M^2} r_0 (1/2 - r_0).$$

Proof. Since A, B have the spectra in $[m, M]$, the spectrum of $B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}$ is in $[\frac{m}{M}, \frac{M}{m}]$. Thus, by the first inequality in (4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} (1-\nu)s_j(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}) + \nu \\ \geq s_j^{1-\nu}(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}) \\ + \tau(\nu)[s_j^{1/2}(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}) - 1]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

for $j = 1, \dots, n$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \det((1-\nu)B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2} + \nu I) \\ = \prod_{j=1}^n [(1-\nu)s_j(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}) + \nu] \\ \geq \prod_{j=1}^n [s_j^{1-\nu}(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}) \\ + \tau(\nu)(s_j^{1/2}(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}) - 1)^2] \\ \geq \prod_{j=1}^n s_j^{1-\nu}(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}) \\ + \tau(\nu)^n \prod_{j=1}^n (s_j^{1/2}(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2}) - 1)^2 \\ = \det(B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2})^{1-\nu} \\ + \tau(\nu)^n \det((B^{-1/2} AB^{-1/2})^{1/2} - I)^2. \end{aligned}$$

This yields that

$$\begin{aligned} \det(A^{1-\nu} B^\nu) + [2\tau(\nu)]^n \det(A\nabla B - A\sharp B) \\ \leq \det((1-\nu)A + \nu B), \end{aligned}$$

Which is the desired inequality.

4. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this work is devoted to give some new refinements and reverses of Young-type inequalities as well as their corresponding operator, trace and determinant versions. The main results of the paper are given in Theorems 3.1, 3.5, 3.8 and 3.9.

TỔNG QUÁT CỦA CÁC BẤT ĐẲNG THỨC KIỂU YOUNG THÔNG QUA NỘI SUY TOÀN PHƯƠNG

Phan Thị Minh⁴, Trần Quỳnh Mai⁵, Dương Quốc Huy⁶

Ngày nhận bài: 15/5/2022; Ngày phản biện thông qua: 10/10/2022; Ngày duyệt đăng: 11/10/2022

TÓM TẮT

Trong bài báo này, chúng tôi đưa ra một số cải tiến mới cho các bất đẳng thức kiểu Young được F. Kittaneh, Y. Manasrah công bố trên các tạp chí *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* (2010) và *Linear Multilinear Algebra* (2011) thông qua lý thuyết nội suy toàn phương. Ứng dụng trực tiếp các bất đẳng thức mới này, chúng tôi thiết lập các phiên bản tương ứng cho ma trận và toán tử.

Từ khóa: Bất đẳng thức Young, Tính lồi, Toán tử dương, Ma trận xác định dương.

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⁴Trường THPT Phan Chu Trinh, Cư Jút, Đắk Nông;

⁵Phòng Đào tạo, Trường Đại học Tây Nguyên, Đắk Lắk;

⁶Khoa Khoa học Tự nhiên và Công nghệ, Trường Đại học Tây Nguyên, Đắk Lắk;

Tác giả liên hệ: Dương Quốc Huy; Tel: 0905616183; Email: duongquochuy@ttn.edu.vn.